

IMPORTANCE OF CHEMICAL PRETREATMENT FOR CARBON FIBRE RECYCLED FROM COMPOSITE BY PYROLYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Recycling of carbon fibre remains one of the imminent global research topics in composite engineering. This work focuses on recovery of carbon fibres from carbon fibre reinforced plastic using a combination of a chemical pre-treatment followed by a pyrolysis process. The chemical pre-treatment was achieved using a zinc chloride/ethanol solution catalytic system. The pyrolysis process was conducted in a thermogravimetric analyser (TGA). The effect of such pre-treatment on the prepreg surface morphology and elemental composition were investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (SEM/EDS). A non-treated prepreg was also investigated for benchmarking. After the thermal pyrolysis process, the fibre tensile properties were measured using a single fibre tester, and the surface morphology of recycled carbon fibres was investigated by SEM. Virgin carbon fibres were also included in the study for benchmarking. After pre-treatment, some tiny cracks appeared on the surface of carbon fibre prepreg. During the pyrolysis process, the devolatilisation temperature of the pre-treated prepreg reduced by around 20-30°C and the peak temperature was 40-50°C lower compared to that of the non-treated prepreg. After pyrolysis in nitrogen with a small amount of air, loose carbon fibres were recovered, and their surface was clean. The chemical pre-treatment process reduces the pyrolysis temperature and oxidation time effectively compared to the conventional pyrolysis process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites have unique combination of low-weight, high elasticity modulus and high strength properties compared with traditional metallic materials and other fibre reinforced composites [1]. A large proportion of CFRP are manufactured using thermoset resin (such as epoxy) as the matrix due to its high thermal stability, good mechanical performance and low cost [2]. The high specific performance serves as the driving force to aid the epoxy based CFRP to dominate the composite markets, meeting the consumer demands [3]. On the other hand, it poses a great threat to the environment at the end of its service life. Industries face a significant challenge in recycling these composites mainly due to their irreversible cross-linked structure of the epoxy matrix. In order to deal with the ever-increasing end-of-life parts and manufacturing wastes, a variety of recycling technologies such as fluidised bed, pyrolysis and solvolysis have been studied intensely across the globe [4]. Among the mentioned technologies, pyrolysis is the most preferable option and is being practised by established companies, such as ELG Carbon Fibre Ltd and Carbon Conversions Inc. This is mainly because the recycled carbon fibre from pyrolysis process retains relatively high mechanical properties and requires less recycling energy in comparison to the other technologies[5, 6].

Conventional pyrolysis treats composite waste at high temperature in an inert environment to convert thermoset matrix into volatiles and char. The volatiles can potentially be further processed for

energy recovery or being used as a feedstock for manufacture of lower molecular weight chemicals. The char, however, remains on the surface of the recovered carbon fibre. The amount of char residue depends on resin chemical molecular structure, for example, the presence of aromatic and other cyclic structures in epoxy resin structure promote the char formation during the pyrolysis process [7]. An extra oxidation process, at a temperature ranging from 600-650 °C [6, 8], is thus necessary for char removal so that clean carbon fibre can be recovered. However, it has been reported that the mechanical performance of the recovered carbon fibre can be degraded by the oxidation process [6]. In this paper, we proposed to introduce an extra chemical pre-treatment process using a zinc chloride (ZnCl_2)/ethanol catalyst system to initiate a breakdown of the cross-linked structure of the epoxy matrix before subjecting the composite to the conventional pyrolysis process, in order to reduce the negative impact the oxidation process causes on the recovered carbon fibre.

Unlike in the past, strong acid [9] or alkali solution [10] was used in dissolving epoxy matrix in chemical recycling approach, a milder environment has been reported recently from the use of Lewis acids, such as ZnCl_2 and magnesium chloride (MgCl_2) in solvents like water and ethanol. A CFRP waste ($T_g > 210^\circ\text{C}$) was effectively decomposed in a ZnCl_2 /ethanol (20wt.%) catalytic system at 190°C for 5h, the resin degradation ratio was 89.8% [11]. Matthew J. Keith's research demonstrated that ZnCl_2 /acetone/water (0.05M) system was an effective catalyst to dissolve more than 94% epoxy resin and the process could be shortened with higher temperature, i.e. from 1.5 hours to 45 minutes by increasing temperature from 290°C to 300°C [12]. Furthermore, the epoxy composites could be completely dissolved in a molten ZnCl_2 at 360°C in 80 min under standard pressure, due to the fracture of the C–N bonds in the epoxy matrix by the catalytic action of Zn^{2+} ions [13].

In this work, we aim to apply the pre-treatment process to reduce char formation in the pyrolysis stage and ultimately clean carbon fibre could potentially be recycled in a shorter oxidation duration as this not only reduces energy consumption, but mechanical performance of the recycled fibre can be better preserved due to the reduced oxidative damage at high temperature. First, effect of the pre-treatment on prepreg morphology and elemental composition were investigated via SEM and EDS analysis. Then a TGA unit was used to establish the effectiveness of the pre-treatment process by comparing the degradation profiles of the treated specimens against a control unit, which had not been pre-treated. Tensile properties of the fibres recovered from these samples were measured via a single fibre tester.

2 MATERIAL AND MATHOD

2.1 Material

A standard unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy prepreg made of Toray[®] T700s-12K carbon fibre and epoxy resin was provided by Aojing[®] Composite Company, Shanghai, China. The epoxy resin content was 37 wt.%, as provided by the manufacturer's data. The prepreg was first cured at 140°C for 2 hours, then it was cut into a size of 25 mm × 25 mm and immersed in a zinc chloride/ethanol catalyst solution for a chemical pre-treatment process. The analytical reagent zinc chloride powder and analytical reagent ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) were provided by Macklin[®] chemical technology co. LTD and Hushi[®] Lab. Equipment co. LTD in Shanghai, China, respectively.

2.2 Chemical pre-treatment process

The catalyst solution was prepared by dissolving ZnCl_2 powder (40wt.%) in 150ml of ethanol in a beaker and was heated up to 80°C using a magnetic stirrer. Cured prepreg was immersed in the solution for 2 hours with constant stirring to ensure homogeneous treatment. Top of the beaker was sealed to prevent the solution from volatilization. After the chemical process, the treated sample was washed with distilled water for several times, then was dried in an oven at 80°C for 24 hours.

2.3 Thermal pyrolysis process

After the pre-treatment process, 20 mg dried sample with a size of 5 mm × 4 mm was placed in a small alumina crucible for thermal pyrolysis using an SDT Q600 thermogravimetric analyser from TA Instruments, Delaware, US. Then the sample was heated to 650°C with a heating rate of 200°C/min and was held isothermally for 30min. 120 ml compressed air was first injected to the furnace before starting the heating process, then a nitrogen gas flowrate of 50 ml/min was introduced for both of the heating and isothermal stages. The non-treated prepreg was also pyrolyzed in the same thermal profile for benchmarking, and the mass loss of treated prepreg and non-treated prepreg were analysed.

2.4 Characterization

Surface morphology of the recovered carbon fibres and prepreps were characterised using a Zeiss® Sigma VP scanning electron microscope with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Elemental composition of the prepreg was determined by using an Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) via an x-act quantitative silicon drift detector supplied by Oxford Instruments, UK, which is attached to the existing SEM unit. The single fibre tensile properties of virgin and recovered carbon fibre were determined by LEX820 tensile tester (Dia-Stron, UK) and conducted in accordance with ISO11566. 20 samples were tested with the gauge length of 4 mm and load cell of 1N.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal pyrolysis for carbon fibre recovery

The thermal pyrolysis behaviour of pre-treated and non-pre-treated prepreg in nitrogen atmosphere were investigated and their mass loss profile over the temperature are shown in Fig. 1. For the non-treated sample, after a marginal drop at the early stage of the heating process, then from around 410°C, the profile undergoes a sharp drop in mass and reaching a relatively flat plateau region. Then the mass continues to drop when the temperature was maintained at 650°C. The initial marginal drop was mainly due to moisture lost, whilst conversion of epoxy matrix into volatiles attributed to the sharp lost in mass. Same pattern was observed from the treated sample, but the start temperature of sharp mass loss is around 390°C. In addition, the mass loss of pre-treated prepreg was lower than the non-treated prepreg, which probably due to some resin had been removed in the early pre-treatment process. DTG curves of the corresponding samples are showed in Fig. 2 and both show only one peak, which can be attributed to the epoxy resin devolatilisation, a fundamental mechanism of pyrolysis process[14] in recovery of carbon fibre. It can be seen that the peak of the pre-treated sample was further to the left, indicating that the devolatilisation stage commenced and finished at lower temperatures[15]. The devolatilisation temperature of treated composite reduced by around 20-30°C and the peak temperature was 40-50°C lower. Therefore, the chemical pre-treatment process was proved to be effectively in reducing the pyrolysis temperature.

Figure 1 The mass change with temperature (TG curve) for pre-treated prepreg and non-treated prepreps.

Figure 2 The derivative of mass change with temperature (DTG curve) of pre-treated and non-treated prepreps.

In addition, at the end of the TGA test, it was found that the non-treated samples still remained intact and stiff, as shown in Fig.3(a), indicating a significant presence of pyrolytic char residues on the fibre surface. However, it is evident that loose fibres were recovered from the pre-treated samples, as shown Fig.3(b) and this was achieved with the injection of oxygen to the TGA chamber prior to the heating process. It is worth to highlight that the non-treated samples were also subjected to the same pyrolytic condition but the initial injection of oxygen had no effect on the removal of char residues. Such reductions in pyrolysis temperature and char formation from the pre-treated samples are attributed to the combined effects of the ZnCl₂/ethanol catalyst system: ethanol has a high swelling ability to open up the epoxy structure in the prepreg to facilitates penetration of ZnCl₂ catalyst to cause cleaving of C-N bonds in the epoxy's cross-linked 3D structures[11, 16].

Figure 3 Pyrolysis solid product from (a) non pre-treated and (b) pre-treated prepregs

3.2 Single fibre tensile test

	Virgin carbon fibre	Recycled carbon fibre
Diameter (micron)	6.44±0.32	6.01 ± 0.46
Tensile modulus (GPa)	212.22 ± 19.43	208.91 ± 17.29
Tensile strength (MPa)	4473.81± 350.68	4012.49± 387.76

Table 1: The tensile properties virgin carbon fibre and recycled carbon fibre.

Tensile properties of the recovered carbon fibres were characterized by using a single fibre tester and the results are presented in Table 1, which also includes data measured from the virgin carbon fibres. No significant change in the tensile modulus was observed. The average diameter and tensile strength of virgin carbon fibre is 6.44 micron and 4473.81MPa. However, after the chemical pre-treatment and pyrolysis process, the diameter and tensile strength decreased about 7% and 10% respectively. Degradation in diameter and tensile strength have been observed from fibre recovered from conventional pyrolysis process [6], however, due to the prolonged oxidation process for char removal at high temperature, 28% reduction in tensile strength had been reported by Lopez et al.[17]. Pimenta & Pinho[18] also reported the importance in controlling the pyrolysis condition in avoiding significant drop in fibre diameter and tensile strength, which could be as high as 21% and 84% respectively. In this work, carbon fiber retained almost 90% of tensile strength of the virgin carbon fiber and required no further oxidation process, confirming the benefit of the pre-treatment process.

3.3 Elemental analysis

The elemental analysis of prepreg before and after the chemical pre-treatment was determined by SEM/EDS test and the results are listed in Table 2. The non-pretreated prepreg consists of 84.68 wt% of carbon content. After the chemical pre-treatment, the value decreased significantly to 77.69 wt%. The decrease in carbon content indicates the partial dissolution of epoxy matrix to the zinc chloride/ethanol catalyst system.

Surface elemental composition of the carbon fibre recovered from the pre-treated sample after thermal pyrolysis was also analysed. Unsurprisingly carbon was the main element found from the recovered fibre surface, but it is important to note that no traces of Zn and Cl elements were detected. The vaporization temperature of $ZnCl_2$ is around 400 °C[19], which is much lower than the 650 °C pyrolytic temperature undertaken in this study. The absence of Zn and Cl elements on the recycled carbon fibre surface suggests no further cleaning process is required.

Element (wt.%)	Non-treated prepreg	Pre-treated prepreg	Recycled carbon fibre
C	84.68	77.69	98.29
O	15.32	14.42	1.71
Cl	-	4.88	-
Zn	-	3.01	-

Table 2: The surface element for non-treated prepreg and pre-treated prepreg.

3.4 Surface morphology analysis

The effect of chemical pre-treatment on prepreg surface morphology is depicted in SEM pictures shown in Fig.5. Without the pre-treatment, the morphology of the as-received prepreg is shown in Fig.5(a) and can be seen from that the fibres were fully covered by the epoxy resin and exhibited a smooth morphology. On the contrary, as shown in Fig.5(b), with the chemical pre-treatment, the prepreg exhibited a rough morphology together with the presence of cracks and tiny voids in the epoxy matrix. The change in surface morphology indicated the effectiveness of the pre-treatment process to initiate a breakdown of the cross-linked structure of the epoxy matrix.

Figure 5 The SEM image of carbon fibre prepreg before (a) and after (b) the pre-treatment.

Surface morphology of the recovered carbon fibre with and without pre-treatment were also investigated via SEM analysis to evaluate the effects of chemical pre-treatment. Comparison was made against with virgin carbon fibre and the results are shown in Fig.6. From Fig.6 (a, b), it can be seen that virgin carbon fibres show a clean and smooth surface. Similar clean surface finish was also observed from fibre recovered from the pre-treated samples, as shown in Fig.6 (c, d), except for the

presence of some fine char particles scatter on the surface. However, Fig.6 (e, f) shows a significant amount of char still remain in the sample without the pre-treatment process. These SEM pictures highlight the effectiveness of the pre-treatment process in reducing the char residue.

Figure 6 The SEM images of virgin carbon fibre (a, b), pre-treated sample after pyrolysis (recycled carbon fibre) (c, d) and non-treated sample after pyrolysis (e, f).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effectiveness of pre-treating composite in the zinc chloride/ethanol catalyst system prior to the pyrolysis process has been demonstrated. It has lowered the devolatilisation temperature of CFRP prepreg by around 20-30°C and the peak pyrolytic temperature has been reduced by 40-50°C, compared to that of the non-treated prepreg. The initial injection of small amount of oxygen to the TGA chamber before the pyrolysis process resulted in clean and loose carbon fibres to be recovered from the pre-treated prepreg. This eliminates the need for the extra oxidation process, a common practice in the conventional pyrolysis process for the removal of char residues. The recovered fibre contains no trace of Zn and Cl elements and has tensile stiffness similar to virgin carbon fibre and retains 90% of the tensile strength.

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